

ヒトの脳における同期的活動 に関する私達の研究の経緯

— The progress of our study on synchronous activity in the human brain —

1968

T. Sohmiya and K. Sohmiya Experimental studies on binocular rivalry by flickering-method J. Physiol. Soc. Jap. 30, 943-947. [English abstract].

○Perceptual grouping や figure-ground segregation を意識の original pattern と考え、それらを量的に究明できる実験法を考案した。この方法は融合法と区別するため後に消失法と改名した。

[Perceptual grouping and figure-ground segregation are original patterns of visual awareness or consciousness. From this viewpoint, we devised a new experimental method that can examine quantitatively them. This was called later 'suppression method' for distinction from 'fusion-method' (see Sohmiya & Sohmiya, Perceptual and Motor Skills, 1990, 70, 515-522; R-11).]

1973 (R-2)

T. Sohmiya [Measurement of strength of pattern in the human brain: study on form perception by a new experimental method.] [Proceedings of the 37th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association.] Pp. 122-123.

○近接、閉合、よい形、よい連続といった Gestalt law of grouping が脳活動の同期に関係することを示す最初の報告。

[The first report of the experimental results, suggesting that the Gestalt law of grouping such as proximity, closure, good Gestalt or good continuity is involved in synchronization of the brain activity.]

1976a (R-3)

T. Sohmiya [Explanation of Gestalt qualities in terms of synchronization of strength of pattern.] [Proceedings of the 40th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association.] Pp. 449-450.

○ヒトの visual cortex における stimulus-evoked oscillatory synchronization の報告。
これは Singer et al's report (Soc. Neurosci. Abstr. 404, 3, 1987) よりも 11 年早い。

Report of the stimulus-evoked oscillatory synchronization in the visual cortex of humans. This report is 11 years earlier than Singer et al's report (Soc. Neurosci. Abstr. 404, 3, 1987). 同封文書5-a 参照。 [See enclosed document 5-a.]

○ パターンの強さが観察時間の関数として周期的に振動することを実証し、次いで 近接、類同、閉合、よい連続、よい形などのゲシュタルト要因が各要素のパターンの強さの同期的振動に起因することを実験的に証明した。

[We proved that 'strength of pattern' (see English paper, Percep. and Motor Skills, 1990, 70, 515-522: R-11) periodically oscillates as a function of duration of observation time and then that the Gestalt law of grouping such as proximate, similarity, closure, good continuity, and good form originates in synchronization between the strength of pattern of each element.]

○ 意識に関する同期仮説の提唱 [Proposal of synchronization-hypothesis on consciousness]

上記の結果から、皮質における同期的振動の概念が自意識を含む人間のすべての精神的活動を特徴づけ説明できる最も有効な原理であると提言した。 [From the above experimental results on the Gestalt law of grouping, we offered that the concept of synchronized oscillations in the cerebral cortex is the most effective idea as a principle which may characterize and explain all of mental activities in the human brain inclining self-consciousness.

これは意識に関する Crick & Koch's 同期説 (see Scientific American September 1992 "The problem of consciousness" by F. Crick & C. Koch and Scientific American December 1995 "The puzzle of conscious experience" by D. J. Chalmers, P. 82; R-4) よりも 16 年早い。 [This is 16 years earlier than Crick and Koch's synchronization-hypothesis on consciousness (see Science American September 1992 "The problem of consciousness" by F. Crick & C. Koch; Scientific American December 1995 "The puzzle of conscious experience" by D. J. Chalmers, P. 82; R-4).]

1976b (R-5)

T. Sohmiya and K. Sohmiya [Fundamental study on pattern recognition by a new experimental method.] Nagoya: Maruzen. [English abstract] (see Pp. 81-91).

○ ヒトの脳においてパターンが強さが観測時間の関数として周期的に振動していることを実験的に証明した。 [In the human brain we proved experimentally that the strength of pattern periodically oscillates as a function of duration of observation time.]

○ 近接、類同、閉合、よい連続、よい形などのゲシュタルト要因が距離的に離れた構成部分のパターンの強さの同期的振動に起因することを理論的、実験的に立証した。 [It was verified theoretically and experimentally that Gestalt factors such as proximity, similarity, closure, good continuity, and good Gestalt depend on synchronized oscillations between strength of pattern of spatially distributed components.]

- 図地分化の難易が各構成要素のパターンの強さの同期的振動の生起の難易に依存することが示された。 [It was illustrated that the hardness (or ease) of figure-ground segregation depends on how hard (or easy) the occurrence of synchronized oscillations in the strength of pattern of each component is.]

1978 (R-6)

T. Sohmiya [Examination of a basic precondition of psychophysical research.] [A symposium in Proceedings of the 42nd Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association.] P. S1.

- 自意識を含む意識の科学的な研究の重要性の強調 [Emphasis on the importance of scientific approaches of consciousness and self-consciousness.]

1980a (R-7)

T. Sohmiya [Analysis of cerebral function in man by interaction between left and right visual systems: a breach in the study of the human brain.] [Proceedings of the 44th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association.] P. 187.

- ヒトの脳機能を解明するために考案した三つの精神物理学の実験法（消失法、融合法、同調法）の発表。 [Report of three psychophysical methods (suppression method, fusion method, and synchronization method) that were devised to clarify the mechanisms of the human brain.]

- 脳活動の統一性は脳の全体系のレベルで生じている同期的振動に起因し、その同期的リズムはヒトの脳のすべての精神的活動の基盤であると再度主張した。 [Again, we emphasized that the coherent properties of the brain activity result from synchronous oscillations at the level of the overall control of the brain and that its synchronous rhythm is a crucial determinant in all of mental activities of the human brain.]

- 脳研究の突破口は皮質に生じている同期的振動を一点測定ではなく全体的同時的測定によって検証し、その発生機構をつきとめることであると明言した。 [We declared that a breach in the brain research is to verify the occurrence of synchronized oscillations in the cortex by simultaneous recordings from large groups of neurons but not by recordings from one cell with one micro-electrode and to clarify the processes and mechanisms of the generation of synchronization.]

1980b (R-8)

T. Sohmiya [Analysis of cerebral function in man by interaction between left and right visual systems: rhythm at the level of the overall control of the system that generates Gestalt.] [Proceedings of the 22nd Annual Convention of the Japanese Association of Educational Psychology.] Pp. 267-268.

○ 刺激の空間的な形態によって synchronous rhythm が発生することを示す実験の再報告。 [It was again reported that the generation of synchronous rhythm is involved in the spatial configuration of the stimuli.]

○ 一本の微小電極による一点測定から全体的同時的測定への移行の必要性と緊急性の再主張。 [Repeated emphasis on the necessity and the emergency of translation from one point measurement by the use of one electrode to overall simultaneous measurement.]

1981 (R-9)

T. Sohmiya [Analysis of cerebral function in man by interaction between left and right visual systems: rhythm that generates coherent figures.] [Proceedings of the first Annual Convention of the Japanese Association of Japan Creativity Society.] P. 13.

○ ヒトの脳において、パターンの各構成成分の strength of pattern が周期的に振動していることを示す再々報告。 [Repeated report, indicating that in the human brain the strength of pattern of each component consisting of a pattern periodically oscillates.]

○ パターンの全体的特性は Neurons の synchronous rhythmic activity に起因すると再度主張した。 [It was again stated that a coherent property of pattern originates in synchronous rhythmic activity of neurons.]

○ 一本の微小電極記録による一点測定から全体的同時的記録に進み、ニューロンの同期的振動活動を確認するよう神経科学者に再び要請した。 [A redemand on neuroscientists for confirmation of the occurrence of synchronous oscillatory activity of neurons by overall simultaneous recordings but not by one point recordings with one microelectrod.]

● In 1981, Christoph von der Malsburg offered an intriguing solution of the problem of visual binding. He said that the neurons involved might bind by briefly synchronizing their patterns of activity (R-1, P. 856).

For a while von der Malsburg's depression was justified — there was no experimental support for his idea (R-1, P.856).

1986a (R-10)

T. Sohmiya [Rhythmic activity in the human brain as the mechanisms underlying the generation of 'pattern'.][Proceedings of the 50th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association.] P.152.

○ Gestalt law of grouping と同様 figure-ground segregation も脳皮質におけるパターンの強さの synchronized oscillations によると主張した。 [We stated that figure-ground segregation as well as Gestalt law of grouping depends on synchronized oscillations in strength of pattern in the visual cortex of humans.]

○ 1980 (R-7) と 1981 (R-8) に、同期的リズム活動は脳の全体的活動の時間経過を連続記録することによって実験的に確かめ得ることを予測したが、この報告でその成果への近々の期待が述べられた。 [In 1980 (R-7) and 1981 (R-8), we predicted that synchronized rhythmic activity in the brain can verify experimentally by continuous recordings on temporal progress of overall activity in the brain. In this report, we stated expectation of being able to confirm its rhythmic activity in the near future.]

● In 1986, Singer and Mioche were conducting experiments on a part of the visual system (R-1, P. 856).

1986b (R-11)

T. Sohmiya & K. Sohmiya Periodicity of strength of pattern in binocular rivalry. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 61, 843-846.

○ English paper reporting that the strength of pattern periodically oscillates as a function of duration of observation time.

● Neither Singer nor Mioche was thinking about von der Malsburg's theory (R-1, P. 856).

● If Singer hadn't been familiar with Freeman's and von der Malsburg's work, he says, he might have thought of the 40-hertz oscillations as nothing more than a curiosity (R-1, P.857).

1987

● C. M. Gray & W. Singer *Soc. Neurosci. Abstr.* 404, 3.

1989

● C. M. Gray, P. Konig, A. K. Engel & W. Singer *Nature* 338, 334-337.

1992

● F. Crick & C Koch *Scientific American* September 1992, 153-159.

Proposal of synchronization-hypothesis on consciousness on the basis of Singer et al's experimental results.

(R-4) D. J. Chalmers (*Scientific American* December 1995: The puzzle of conscious experience; P.82) stated that "Consider the hypothesis put forward by neurobiologists F. Crick and C. Koch. They suggest consciousness may arise from certain oscillations in the cerebral cortex, which become synchronized as neuron fire 40 times per second".

1994 (R-12)

T. Sohmiya & K. Sohmiya What is a crucial determinant in anorthoscopic perception? Perceptual and Motor Skills, 78, 987-998.

○ Anorthoscopic perception was explained in terms of 'anorthoscopic motion' complementary to apparent motion, which results from synchronization of each motion of parts of a pattern viewed through a slit.

1995

T. Sohmiya & K. Sohmiya Explanation of illusory contours in terms of strength of pattern and its spread effect. Perceptual and Motor Skills, 81, 1003-1020.

(R-13)

○ It was stated that we had claimed since 1976 that the Gestalt law of grouping originates in synchronization between the strength of pattern of each component of stimulus configuration, that is, the synchronization is a cause and the Gestalt law of grouping is a secondary outcome of the synchronization in the strength of pattern.

現時点の最重要問題は、F. Crick への手紙 (Feb. 21, 1996) で述べたように、私達が知覚で見出した秒単位のゆっくりとした同期的振動と Singer グループが見出したニューロン活動のミリ秒単位の極めて速い同期的振動とを理論的、実験的に関係づけことであると私達は考えている。 [We believe that the most important problem at present, as stated in our letter to F. Crick (February 21, 1996), is to combine theoretically and experimentally slow synchronous oscillations in perception of the order of second by us and extremely fast ones in neuronal activity of the order of millisecond by Singer's group.]

Please correct errors if any.

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